

CHALLENGES IN LISTENING COMPREHENSION IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

Makhmudova Dilshodakhon

The Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Head teacher of Fergana academic lyceum

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Annotation: This literature review analyzes how to develop listening comprehension skill in second language teaching and learning process. The reader will be aware of a wide range of listening strategies and how to deal with difficulties in language learning path.

Key words: Listening comprehension strategies, cognitive strategies, metacognitive strategies, socio-affective strategies.

Introduction

Listening is an indispensable part of the language learning process. Acquisitions occur only when students get fairly comprehensive input (Krashen, Terrell, Ehrman, & Herzog, 1984). Priollette Andrea Helena (2005) claims that listening is considered as a natural talent that is used as a device to help children improve their comprehension skills. Listening is a core component of everyday life. As Mettine Thanajaro(2000) suggests that as listening comprises a lot of parts of in the everyday life of many people, it is crucial to have good listening proficiency in order to meet listening needs that arise daily. In this research paper, much attention was put on improving the techniques of listening comprehension after analyzing learners' comprehension issues. This paper helps to draw instructors' focus on dealing with the complexity of understanding input by acquiring appropriate and powerful actions. It is believed that the findings of this work will benefit from gaining knowledge of listening comprehension skills.

Listening comprehension strategies

As listening plays the main role in communication skills there has been a wide range of developments in listening especially for second language users. The more appropriate strategy is used the more success will be gained in listening comprehension skills.. The improvement of strategy is important for the training of listening because students can organize and check their very own knowledge and responses. If they have a solid strategy, it improves their comprehension skills as well and their language learning process will become easier. O'Malley and Chamot (1990) claimed that listening comprehension can be based on three strategies.

Cognitive Strategies

Learners use cognitive techniques to gather and interpret information in their memory for future use. If learners have a cognitive strategy, they will be good at dealing with issues and it helps them to accelerate the learning process. Bottom-up and top-down approaches play the main role in listening activities. Vandergrift, L., & Goh, C. (2009) explained that bottom-up processing in listening involves knowing about sounds and phrases, intonation patterns, syllable stress in a speech stream. The top-down approach includes students' understanding of the topic and general meaning. If learners are good at the above-mentioned

patterns of speech, they can connect their background knowledge to understand the information which is coming outside

Metacognitive strategies

O'Malley et al. (1989) claimed that if students have a high level of listening proficiency they can refocus on the listening procedure when their comprehension breaks by using their metacognitive strategies, whereas low-level listeners can not continue listening. Vandergrift (2003) and Abdalhamid (2012) confirmed that

The usage of metacognitive strategies is two times higher in those who are good at listening rather than low-level listeners.

Socio-affective Strategies

Vandergrift (2003) and Abdalhamid (2012) indicated that socio-affective strategies serve students as a tool for collaboration, dealing with comprehension, and lower their anxiety. The less anxiety there is, the higher performance will be during the listening process. It is evident that if students socialize, interact more it helps to break the ice between teachers and fellow students which leads to more self-confidence and motivation for learning. Students should possess low affective filters to perform well during listening activities.

Major challenges in Listening Comprehension

It is true that there are some comprehension problems that require feasible approaches to be good listeners. One should have solid grammar and vocabulary knowledge, discrimination between sounds, and interpret the information. Therefore, listening comprehension demands learners a great deal of cognitive and metacognitive skills. Underwood (1989) indicates seven possible challenges that could be a hindrance to comprehension skills.

First, the fastness of speech is beyond the management of listeners. According to Underwood (1989), it is difficult for learners to comprehend when the speech is too fast.

Second, students do not have an opportunity to ask the teacher to repeat the recording any time and the teacher has difficulties identifying students' comprehension during listening.

Third, there are some words that are difficult to understand for learners, and in this case, they stop listening and begin to interpret the meaning of the new words. As a result, it affects negatively other parts of the listening activity.

Fourth, listeners may not recognize the language patterns when the speaker shifts their tone of speech. Students can understand formal language by knowing discourse markers such as initially, secondly whereas they cannot decipher sudden change of speech, volume, body language in an informal context.

Fifth, concentration is the next hindrance for language learners during listening. A small interference can have a negative effect on comprehension. Moreover, the quality of recorded materials, accent and cultural differences are other challenges that students can encounter while listening.

Useful Suggestions for Instructors

To address some issues of learners' listening comprehension instructors should follow some of these recommendations.

1. Instructors should explain the rules of pronunciation and ask them to learn the way in which English people speak. It enables them to differentiate between American and British English
2. Listening materials should be allocated based on the learners' language level. For example, for beginners, simple activities are applicable, for higher levels more complex activities should be distributed.
3. Instructors should comment on their students' mistakes and give essential feedback on their overall performance because it can shape their self-esteem, self-correction, and boost their motivation towards the listening activities.
4. Instructors should have enough knowledge and expertise in their field to be role models for students. It can help students to increase motivation and to be proficient user in the target language.
5. Instructors should ask their learners to create an English atmosphere and advise them to have English speaking friends to interact and communicate with them quite often.

Conclusion

Educators should know the importance of listening tasks in the language learning process and they should allocate the activities according to the students' level. Much emphasis should be put on improving listening strategies and they can be a boost for other skills as well. Krashen's Input Hypothesis (1985) states instructors should provide material and language that is a little bit higher than the learners' existing proficiency to increase as it creates some challenges to help them develop, but they should not be more complex in order not to discourage them. This research has analyzed some causes which lead to inappropriate approaches in English learners' understanding when they are listening following useful approaches to deal with these issues to develop listening ability. It is believed that due to the beneficial factors of this observation, I will contribute to the educators and learners' further development of language learning path.

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